

Influence of *Shafii* Jurisprudence on Marriage Guardianship on Islamic Courts in Zanzibar

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Abstract:

Zanzibar is located along the East coast of Africa and the region is part of the United Republic of Tanzania. The region allows Islamic law in the adjudication process on Muslim Personal matters such as: marriage divorce, inheritance and other related matters. Islamic Courts in Zanzibar are known as Kadhis Courts. In fact, Muslim judges preside in Islamic courts they are referred to as Kadhis. The judges of these courts make use of the Quran and Sunnah of the Prophet Mohammad to adhere to Islamic law principles. Marriage is a vital institution under Islamic law which is seen a part of the Muslim identity. The institution is guided by primary legal requirements and secondary legal requirements. Though marriage guardianship forms part of the secondary requirements, it is an essential norm for a valid marriage under Islamic law. This paper examines the impact of Shafii jurisprudence on marriage guardianship on Islamic courts in Zanzibar during the post-colonial era. The discourse uses doctrinal and non-doctrinal approaches and makes useful recommendations.

Keywords: Impact. *Shaffi* Jurisprudence, Marriage Guardianship, Islamic Courts, Zanzibar.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Islamic jurisprudence is an integral part of Islamic law which varies from one region to another. The official jurisprudence of the people of Zanzibar is the *Shafii* jurisprudence since the time immemorial. But this paper examines the impact *Shafii* jurisprudence on marriage guardianship on Islamic courts in Zanzibar–Tanzania during the post-colonial era. This paper addresses the divine position on the issue of marriage guardianship in Islam, classification of marriage guardianship, and its significance as a necessary ingredient of Muslim marriage. Similarly, the paper highlights on marriage guardianship under Islamic law, and the perspective of *Shafii* jurisprudence on the matter. In addition, the paper discusses juristic overview on the matter at hand. Furthermore, the study identifies the significance of Muslim Marriage. The study uses court jurisprudence from Zanzibar to illustrate the impact of *Shafii* jurisprudence on marriage guardianship.

2. MARRIAGE GUARDIANSHIP IN ISLAM

Muslim women's rights are the subject of discussions and a great deal of debate in the contemporary era.¹ Muslim women at such forum tend to argue in favor of Islam because of their knowledge of the ideals of Islam.² It is worth noting, that many aspects of the life in Muslim nations as it relates to women and family law are based on inherited medieval Islamic jurisprudence.³ An overview of patriarchal Islamic jurisprudence from within the tradition, suggests that a woman must be familiar with the logic of Islamic jurisprudence and its basic principles of reasoning. Over the centuries this mode of logic has placed women on disadvantageous position. Despite their shortcomings, the patriarchal jurists were products of their times.⁴ This is because laws change with changes in time, place and custom.⁵ Marriage is one of the most significant fundamentals in Islam from the classical era to the modern era and is seen as an integral part of Muslim identity.⁶

According to Islamic jurisprudence, the concept is God ordained that marriage is the union of the opposite sex.⁷ Marriage is a recognized tradition of the Prophet and considered a contract between two equal partners. Islam speaks of marriage as love, sympathy and peace of mind.⁸ A second opinion is required under Islamic jurisprudence from a man of experience is needed in choosing a good and suitable husband. This is the cardinal goal of

¹ Meetings of the UN Fourth Conference on Women and the NGO Forum, held in Huairou, China, August, 1985. Some participants in the NGO Forum observed the rise of spirituality among women as influenced by the sharp rise in the number of sessions addressing matters relating to religion or spirituality. Kharofa, A.E. *Islamic Family Law a Comparative Study with Other Religions*. Selangor, International Law Book Services, 2004.

² Sisters in Islam, a Malaysian women's organization, issued a press release in Huairou, August 1995, stating that two dominant and opposing views on Islam emerged in the NGO Forum at Huairou the release characterizes the first view as focused on comparing the ideals of Islam with the reality and ills of the Western world. The second view, it adds, rejects religion as a reaction against Islamic conservation and abuses committed in the name of Islam.

³ Abd Al-Halim Abu Shuqqah. *Tahrir Al-Mar'ah Fi Asr Al- Risalah*. Vol. 5, Passim, Kuwait, Dar al-Qalam, 1990.

⁴ *Ibid*.

⁵ Ibn Ashur, A. *Treatise on Maqasid al-Shariah*. El-Mesawi, M.T. Trans. Selangor, Islamic Book Trust, 2006, p. 85-115.

⁶ Atangana, H.A.K., *Islam and Marriage in the 21st Century*. <http://www.zawaj.com/articles/marriage21stcentury>. Html. Accessed on 3/1/2018.

⁷ Quran 24:32.

⁸ Rafiq, A. *Role of Guardian in Muslim Women's Marriage: A Study In The Light Of Religious Texts*. *International Journal of Innovative Science, Engineering & Technology*, Volume 2 Issue 4. April 2015, p.1254.

a guardian or *walii* to guard the woman who is his ward. Marriage guardian under Islamic jurisprudence is seen as a position of authority or control over others. Hence, a person who has the authority to give a woman in marriage is defined as Marriage Guardian or *Walii* under Islamic law.⁹ Linguistically, the word *wilayah* in Arabic means family relationship, and is of Arabic root. According to Sharia the concept refers to the ability to perfect a contract and put it into effect. *Walii* or guardian from Islamic jurisprudence stand-point is the person who can put into effect someone else's marriage contract whether this someone is a young woman or man.¹⁰

Furthermore, scholars define it as the legal authority invested in a person fully qualified and competent to protect the interest and rights of another person who is not capable of doing so independently. Similarly, an inexperienced person may also benefit from the protection of a guardian. This authority is vested in the father or nearest male relative over minors and insane. Scholars and jurists back up their justification for Marriage Guardianship as an essential requirement of a valid marriage with textual sources from the Quran and Sunnah.¹¹

3. DIVINE POSITION ON MARRIAGE GUARDIANSHIP

Divine evidence highlights on understanding the concept for in Islam reference is made to verses taken from the Quran to explain guardianship. Muslims claim that God is the guardian of all the faithful. Those that are mentally incapable to perform an act, the guardian may determine his or her faith.¹² Islamic jurisprudence recommends that Muslims are in better position to perform the role of guardianship to one another. There are divine verses of the Quran that shed light on the role of guardian in the marriage of a Muslim woman.¹³ According to Muslim jurists, the role of the marriage guardian may be defined as a right conferred on him by law that gives him the mandate to act on his ward's behalf with or without her wishes.¹⁴ Further, the guardian may be regarded as a duty specifically given by law and under his responsibility for the ward's welfare. On the other hand, Muslim jurists argue that marriage guardianship seems to be a duty rather than a right of the guardian, while other jurists see it at least a mixture of both.¹⁵ In the first instance, it makes grounds for a guardian in marriage since it encourages the guardian to arrange the marriage of unmarried men and women. The provision does not distinguish between marriage guardianship of unmarried men or women.¹⁶ Similarly, textual evidence from the verses of the Quran indicates that only men who wish to propose a woman for marriage are taken care of by the holy book.¹⁷ Besides, Islamic values take into

⁹ Ibid.

¹⁰ Siddiqi, M. I. *The Family Laws of Islam*. Delhi, International Islamic Publishers, 1988, p.71.

¹¹ Ibid, p. 71.

¹² Quran 2: 25 & Quran 2:282

¹³ Qaitb, S. In the Shade of the Quran Fi Zilal al-Quran. (Vol. 13), Salahi, A. Trans & Ed. London, The Islamic Foundation & Islam Online Net, 2005. Ibrahim, A. Family Law in Malaysia. Kuala Lumpur, Malayan Law Journal, 1997.

¹⁴, Hummudah, A 'A. Op cit, pp.74 -75.

¹⁵ Ibid.

¹⁶ Ibid.

¹⁷ Quran 4:25

consideration that the guardian should obtain the consent of women and give them their dowers. Ultimately, the guardians are expected to act in the ward's interest and conformity with her wishes.¹⁸

4. CLASSIFICATION OF MARRIAGE GUARDIANSHIP

Muslim jurists have classified marriage guardianship under different categories of Islamic jurisprudence. Textual evidence from the Quran and the traditions of the Prophet are used to buttress their positions. *Shafii* jurisprudence divides guardianship of marriage into two, namely general and specific guardianship.¹⁹ Under the first classification, the general guardian has a general authority of guardianship over women in an Islamic State that is a Muslim ruler commands such authority.²⁰ But specific guardian has the authority specifically on daughters, or close relations based on lineage or blood ties. Here the father, grandfather brothers, paternal nephews and paternal uncles fall under this classification.²¹ Another School of thought argues that there are three types of marriage guardian, namely; compulsory guardianship, recommended guardianship and complementary guardianship. The *Shafii* School of jurisprudence subscribes to compulsory guardianship for women who are mature and virgin as well as decent lady. Complementary guardianship is acknowledged by *Shafii* jurisprudence.²² Other schools of jurisprudence argue in favor of recommended guardianship. This guardianship has to take the permission of the ward before the right may be vested in him, otherwise, the marriage is void.²³

5. GUARDIANSHIP AS NECESSARY INGREDIENT OF MUSLIM MARRIAGE

All Muslims jurists have a common position on the value of *Walii* as an essential requirement of a valid marriage. Although some Muslim jurists argue that guardianship is a conditional requirement.²⁴ *Shafii* jurisprudence concurs to the fact that the guardian is a vital ingredient of a valid marriage. With a caveat the consent of the woman in a marriage contract must not be overlooked.²⁵ Other school of thought, explain that if a woman goes into a marriage contract without a *walii* consent the marriage is kept in view until the guardian approves.²⁶ Otherwise, the marriage is not valid. Furthermore, Muslim jurists are critical that though the consent of guardian is recommended, but argue that guardian may intervene in the marriage of their daughter in certain cases.²⁷ Jurists argue that if the guardian performs in accordance to the laid rules, he approves any marriage

¹⁸Hummudah, Abd al 'Ati, Op.cit, p.75. Vesey-Fitzgerald, Seymour. Muhammad Law: An Abridgement. London, Oxford University Press, 1931, 81-88.

¹⁹ Muhammad, A. et al Protecting Women's Interest (Maslahah in Marriage Through Appointment of a Guardian Wali Under Islamic Law. *Pertanika Journal of Social Science & Humanities*. 23 (S) 75-84, 2015

²⁰ Ibid, p. 76.

²¹ Muhammad, A. et . Ibid, p. 77.

²²Ibid, p. 11.

²³ Ibid, p. 12.

²⁴Aftab H. Status of Women in Islam. Lahore, Law Publishing Company, 1987. See Muhammad, A, Ibrahim, B & Abdul Razak, S. Op.cit, p.77-78.

²⁵ Ibid.

²⁶ Al-Ashqar, U.A.A.A. Ahkam al Zawaj fi Dau 'I al-Kitabwa al-Sunnah.(4th Ed). Amman, Dar al-Nafa'is, 2012.Ali al-Sartawi, M. Fiqh al-Ahwal al-Shakhsiyyah: Al-Zawajwa al-Talaq, Amman, Dar al-Fikh, 2008, p. 40.

²⁷ Ibid, p. 41.

that his principal agrees, provided the marriage fulfills the basic requirements of the Islamic law.²⁸ Thus, the guardian acts as an instrument for negotiation directly with the prospective groom over the terms of the marriage contract. In the same vein, the presence of a third-party guardian allows for better agreements which may not be possible with the absence of the guardian. By extension, the guardian acts as a facilitator of a marriage contract in order to achieve a successful matrimonial outcome. Also, since the guardian is usually from the wife's family, jurists contend that the guardian acts as a protector for Muslim women's interest refers to as *maslahah*.²⁹

Muslim jurists explain public interest as the seeking of benefits and the repelling of harm as directed by the Lawgiver in accordance to the Sunnah of the Prophet.³⁰ The application of the principles of public interest, the existence of guardian in a marriage contract is significant to safeguard negative consequences on the ward.³¹ The justification for a guardian according to Muslim jurists is that his consent to marriage indicates his blessings. Therefore, guardian involvement is vital in ensuring happiness in marriage. Guardianship in marriage is considered as one in-built mechanism in Islamic jurisprudence in preventing marital problems in through proper screening of prospective husband for the sole purpose of safeguarding a happy marriage. Jurists, posit that the role of guardian in marriage assists to avoid unlawful ends. The application of the principle of blocking the means to unlawful ends is known among jurists as *ad al-Dhariah*.

According to Muslim jurists the principle involves lawful acts that may be prohibited as a result of its negative consequences.³² The authority for its applications is found in textual evidence from the verses from the Quran and the Sunnah of the Prophet.³³ The importance of guardian as one of the pillars of marriage is recognized in Zanzibar and Kwara State of Nigeria. Also, the importance of guardian in marriage contacted is as well appreciated in the practice in law and practice in several Muslim nations of the world.³⁴

6. MARRIAGE GUARDIANSHIP UNDER SHAFII JURISPRUDENCE

There is no unified position on the legal role of parents or a guardian in contracting or agreeing to a marriage or the rights of women to determine their spouses either within civil legal jurisprudence or under the Islamic law.³⁵The religious obligation to obtain the

²⁸ Fadel, M. Reinterpreting the Guardian's Role in the Islamic Contract of Marriage: The Case of the Maliki School. *The Journal of Islamic Law* Volume. 3, Number 1, Spring/Summer 1998, pp.1-26.

²⁹ Kamali, M. H, *Principle of Islamic Jurisprudence*. Kuala Lumpur, Ilmiah Publishers, 1998, pp. 158- 160. See Nyazee, I.A.K. *Islamic Jurisprudence (Usul al-Fiqh)*. Lahore, The International Institute of Islamic Thought, 2000, pp. 75- 80.

³⁰ *Ibid*, p. 76.

³¹ Mohammad, A.et el. Protecting Women's Interest Maslahah in Marriage Through Appointment of a Guardian Wali Under Islamic Law. *Pertanika Journal of Social Science & Humanities* 23 (S), 2015, pp.75-84.

³² Nyazee, I.A.K *Islamic Jurisprudence*. Lahore, The International Institute of Islamic Thought, 2000, p. 11.

³³ Quran 6:108.

³⁴ *Ibid*.

³⁵ Ali, K. Consent and Forced Marriage. <http://www.muslimmatrimonial.com/muslim-matrimonials/articles/islamic/marriage/consent-and-forced-marriage.shtml>. Accessed 10th February, 2018. Knowing

woman's consent is based on traditional jurisprudence due to the bride's inexperience, family pressure and norms of modesty and obedience. However, the ultimate goals of guardian permission and women consent is to ensure that both partners freely consent to the intended marriage, allows women to choose their marriage partners. Also, it is to ensure that they are neither obliged to accept arranged or forced marriage nor prevented from entering marriages they have chosen.³⁶

The *Shafii* jurisprudence has a clear position on the right of a woman to choose a husband. This jurisprudence argues that the father has *wilayat al-ijar* over his sane female virgin daughter.³⁷ They rest their argument on the Sunnah of the Prophet which does not recognize *wilayat al-ijar* over the adult woman or a divorcee. Such condition is strictly for the virgin lady.³⁸ This school of jurisprudence has some guiding conditions that should be fulfilled before the father's *wilayat al-ijbar* may be executed over his adult mentally sound virgin daughter.³⁹ These requirements include: there is no conflict between the father and his daughter, which the father takes into consideration is the competency of the suitor, and that ensure that her gift or *mahr al-mithl* is in local currency. Other conditions are the dower does not hinder the marriage; the father makes sure that the husband is caring and does not suffer from serious diseases like leprosy or being blind and the daughter must have visited the holy house in Mecca.⁴⁰

According to the Sunnah, these are the conditions that must be fulfilled before the father has the mandate over his sane virgin daughter to get married without taking her consent or permission into consideration.⁴¹ This mandate is applicable only in cases where the guardian is either the father or the grandfather.⁴² On the widow or a divorcee who intends to remarry, according to the *Shafii* jurisprudence, *wilayat istihbah* and not *wilyah ijbar* is applicable whether the guardian is the father or other male relatives on the father side.⁴³ The widow or divorcee the right to be consulted, the *Shafii* jurisprudence states that clear permission by the adult woman is required for the marriage to be properly conducted.⁴⁴ Muslim scholars and jurists consider the issue of the woman marrying herself or another woman to a proposing candidate. *Shafii* school of thought disallows a woman marrying herself or igniting the steps of marriage without the authority of the guardian.⁴⁵ But

Our Rights: Women's, family laws and customs in the Muslim World .3rd ed. London, Women Living under Muslim Laws, 2006, pp.59-109.

³⁶ Ibid, p. 65.

³⁷ Al-Mastora, M.R.H.A Study of the wife Rights in Islamic Fiqh. A Ph.D. thesis, Birmingham, The Department of Theology, School of Historical Studies, The University of Birmingham, January, 2004, p. 65.

³⁸ Al-Qurubi, M. Al-Jami li-ahkam al-Quran. Volume. 1, Beirut, Dar Al-Kutub Al-Ilmiyyah, n.d, p. 497. Al-Shawkani, M.F.A. Volume. 1, (ed.) Mar'ifah Al-Ghoush, Y. Beirut, Dar Al-Ma'rifah, 1995, p.574.

³⁹ Al-Mastora, M. R. H.Op.cit.p. 67.

⁴⁰ Ibid, p. 69.

⁴¹ Ibid, p. 70.

⁴² Abu Da'ud, A. Sunan A.D. Volume. 2, (Ed.). Al-Da'as,I. U & Al-Sayyid, A. Beirut, Dar al-Hadith, Hadith Number, 2125, 1974, p. 596.

⁴³ Al-Mastora, M. R.H. Op.cit, pp.70-71.

⁴⁴ Al-Dardir, A. S. . Volume. 2, Cairo, Dar Al- Ma'arif, n.d. p. 428.

⁴⁵ Ibid, p. 429.

regarding whether the guardian consented to the marriage or not, the *Shafii* scholars based the justification on evidence from the Quran and Sunnah.⁴⁶

7. JURISTS OVERVIEW ON MARRIAGE GUARDIANSHIP

In contemporary period, classic opinions of the female and their role in Muslim societies are being reviewed not only by modern feminist School of thought, but by the modern scholars. The contemporary school of thought is not only critical to most matters that are concerned to women's rights, but argue on how best to improve the status of women in Islam.⁴⁷ Women in period of ignorance Arabia were subject of discrimination, inhuman treatment, and anti-social vices. The advent of Islam brought changes not only in the area of family law but improved the status of female folks. Similarly, modern Scholars contend that women are victims of ill-treatment in contemporary world.⁴⁸ Feminists are of the opinion that women are treated equally as men. They posit that the women folks are given equal treatment in contemporary socio-cultural outlook.

Ancient religion has assisted the unequal treatment of women gave men the opportunity to dominate women. Thus, some intellectuals explain that religion as the symbol of the oppressed creatures, the soul of a heartless world, just as it the tranquilizer of the people. In addition, notable classic thinkers are of the view that social humiliation of women had its genesis in the ancient times. This group argues that females are not the same as males, therefore subject to lot of inadequacy.⁴⁹ However, some scholars are of the view that the Quran addresses the improvement of women but the position of the divine text is not the same with what is happening in the modern era. Contemporary scholars are the view that female autonomy and female equality together with a body of legal doctrines are not in harmony with the demands of the women rights in modern times.⁵⁰ The cardinal norm of a valid marriage under Islamic law is father's approval of the union, or the approval of another male member of the family. This is an old pre-Islamic Arabia culture incorporated into Islam. The norm differentiated the male and the female and resulted in the necessity of guardianship as an essential requirement of Islamic marriage.⁵¹

In the same vein, Islamic societies discriminate against female children right from birth and regard male children as special gift of the almighty. The birth of such children is usually celebrated. Marriage according to divine verses from the Quran is centered at

⁴⁶ Abdulmajid Ta'amah Halabi, A. Beirut, Dar Al-Ma'rifah, 2000, p. 493.

⁴⁷ Badran, Margot. *Feminism, Islam, and Nation: Gender and the Making of Modern Egypt*. Princeton, Princeton University Press, 1995, pp. 19-21. Najmabadi, Afsanch. *Feminism in an Republic. Years of Hardship, Years of Growth*, in Haddad, Yvonne and Esposito, John (eds.), *Islam, Gender, and Social Change*, New York, Oxford University Press, 1988, pp. 59-84.

⁴⁸ Badran, Margot. *Unifying Women: Feminism Pasts and Presents in Yemen*, Gender and History, Special Issue on Feminism Internationalism, 10, 3, November 1998, and chapter 11 in this volume.

⁴⁹ Aristotle. *The Generation of Animals*. Loeb, Classical Library, 1943, p. 175.

⁵⁰ Hassan, Raffat. *Women's Rights in Islam: Normative Teachings Versus Practice*. Available @ [http://riffathassan.info/wp-content/upload/2014/03/Women's Rights in islam_Normative_Teachings](http://riffathassan.info/wp-content/upload/2014/03/Women's_Rights_in_islam_Normative_Teachings). Pdf Accessed on 9th March, 2018.

⁵¹ Fadel, Mohammad. *Reinterpreting the Guardian's Role in the Islamic Contract of Marriage: The Case of the Maliki School*, *The Journal of Islamic Law*, Volume. 3, Number 1, Spring/Summer, 1998, p.1-26.

protecting the rights of women in the context of marriage. ⁵²The norm is that many young women are married out when they do not understand that marriage is contractual agreement that can be negotiated. The divine book of God highlights that marriage brings a male and female together equality and mutuality. Thus, the doctrine of Quran on matters of marital relation must adhere to accordingly. The patriarchal norm that was inherited from the pre-Islamic era has negative effect on the attitude to women.⁵³

Muslim intellectuals posit that a woman remain part of her control until such woman enters marital relationship and evidence of reliable witnessed that the woman could handle her property or estate. Islam does not agree to the notion of mankind organized in hierarchical arrangement based either on gender, class or race. ⁵⁴ According to Islamic law the most favored in the eye of God are pious man and woman. The divine verses from the Quran are based on the principle of personal responsibility.⁵⁵ Hence the classification of human beings is a criterion based on one's personal moral violation. Islam position was to remedy the negative effects of authoritarian patriarchal structure of pre-Islam era. The major area of reforms was to put in place some mechanisms to assist women in the ugly nature of marital life. One such reform put in place was the concept of *walii* or marriage guardianship introduced to protect the women's right under Islamic law.⁵⁶

Despite the reforms, some contemporary scholars have pin-pointed of some of the weaknesses of marriage guardian from different perspectives. One premise argue that it is a mere review of some man-made practice with the coloration of religion which are unacceptable to internationally accepted norms of human rights, particularly as it is related to the women's rights. Other scholars contend that the difficulty in the interpretation of certain ambiguous divine verse of the Quran resulted in the misinterpretation of such verses that are related to women's rights under Islamic law.⁵⁷

On the other hand, contemporary scholars posit that the issue of male guardianship is in recent times are no longer tenable since women are now breadwinners of their families, hence they function as strong pillars in marital relationship. But pre-modern jurists explain that an extension of power of authority of male guardianship over women is to protect women from being exploited or injured by men. ⁵⁸ Of recent, some contemporary jurists argue that the pre-Arabia position on protection of women is not acceptable in modern era since such protection for women belong to the dark ages in Islamic history

⁵² Ibid.

⁵³ Hassan, Riffat. *Women's Rights in Islam: Normative Teachings Versus Practice*, p. 54.

⁵⁴ Al-Hibri, Azizah. *An Introduction to Muslim Women's Rights*. Window of Faith 51, Webb, Gisela (ed.), Syracuse, Syracuse University Press, 2000, p. 60-62.

⁵⁵ Q 17:15; Q 39:7; and Q 53:38.

⁵⁶ Ibid.

⁵⁷ Coomaraswamy, Radhika. *UN Commission on Human Rights of the Special Rapporteur on Violence against women, its causes and consequences*. E/CN.4/1995/42. November 22, 1994. Para. 66.

⁵⁸ An-Naim, A.A. *Islam and Women's Rights: A Case Study, Women Living under Muslims dossier 14-15, 1996*, p. 7.

during which the society lacked security for the people. And more importantly such era is gone for security has now improved.⁵⁹

Shafii jurisprudence on the other hand, interprets the authority of a guardianship and its limits on the minor because they do not enjoin legal capacity to act for themselves. The accepted position of among the jurists is that the minors, inexperienced, insane and irresponsible individuals, be it male or female must have a guardian under Islamic law. But jurists emphasize that the female must have a guardian and keep mute on that need of male to have a guardian. At the moment there is an ongoing discourse in some Muslim nations on the significance for guardianship for women. But argue the fact that under Islamic law, a married woman is under the jurisdiction of the husband guardianship.⁶⁰

Another school of thought posits that the need for woman guardianship denies them the right of equal rights under the law which is contrary to international expectations. Though, nations with sizeable number of Muslims only deny those with some mental problems to make decisions for their personal usage and those that are minors.⁶¹

Contemporary scholars are of the opinion that the extension to fully competent adult female tampers with women's right in the light of the UN Convention on the Elimination of All Forms of Discrimination since men and women have equal opportunities to use capacity under the International law.⁶² This group argues further, that on the women's rights to enter marriage freely without any hindrance and seeking permission of male guardian on marital matters is seen as a form of discrimination against women.⁶³ Zanzibar has a sizeable number of Muslim population and like other Muslim-majority countries rely on personal law based on Islamic law, which respects marriage as a civil contract and other forms of contract needs mutual agreement of consenting individuals makes an offer (*ijab*) and the other accepts (*qabul*) this norm is an integral part of Arab culture since the classic times.

⁵⁹ Human Rights Watch interview with Dr. Abdullahi, A.A, at King Saud University and member of the National Society for Human Rights, Riyadh, Novenber, 2006.

⁶⁰ El-Alami, Dawoud S. Legal Capacity with Specific Reference to the Marriage Contract. Arab Law Quarterly, Vol. 6, Number. 2, 1992, p.192-195. Human Right Watch interview with Dr. Magel al-Turky, Ministry of Islamic Affairs, Riyah, March 9, 2008

⁶¹ Al-Musnad, Muhammad bin Abdul-Aziz. Islamic Fatawa Regarding Women. Riyadh, Darussalam Publications, 1996, 310-313.

⁶² UN Convention on the Elimination of All Forms of Discrimination against Women (CEDAW), adopted December 18, 1979, G.A. res. 34/180.34 U.N. GAOR Supp.(No. 46) at 193, U.N. Doc. A/34/46, entered into force September 3, 1981, art. 15cr

⁶³ Nasir, Jamal J. The Status of Women under Islamic Law and under Modern Islamic Legislation. London, Graham & Trotman, 1999, p. 9-12.

8. SIGNIFICANCE OF MUSLIM MARRIAGE

Marriage under the Islamic law is the joining of couple together for marital union abiding by the Islamic law principles as clearly stated in the Quran and the Sunnah.⁶⁴ Islam regard marriage as fifty percent of a person's faith and the religion traced the origin of marital relationship to the union of Adam and Eve. With such a union, the man and woman in the relationship live in harmony and peace for the purpose having children and continue the existence of human race.⁶⁵ Divine texts from the verses of Quran explain the common need of equality because God created mankind from a single soul.⁶⁶ Muslim intellectuals do not have a uniform explanation of the word marriage. However, orthodox jurists differ in their notion of the concept.⁶⁷ According to *Shafii* School of thought, they posit that marriage makes available the special right to sexual relationship, which the main aim of joining the man and woman together.⁶⁸

Modern scholars, regard the union as a way of emotional and sexual interaction in other to reduce stress, promote legally binding procreation and assist social interaction through inter-family activities and ultimately enhance group solidarity.⁶⁹ In addition, the aim of marriage is to make individuals to be focused in moral upliftment and ultimately produce morally oriented citizen of the human race. By doing marriage as a platform of spreading useful cultural value of Islam and ensure Islamic identity.⁷⁰ Muslim marriage makes guideline for rights and responsibilities of women under Muslim marital union. Such rules and regulations must be obeyed at all times for peaceful co-existence of the marriage.

Part of the rights of Muslim marriage includes the political and education rights, economic and legal rights.⁷¹ Also, Islamic law makes sure the Muslim women are well maintained by the husband that making available education, feeding clothing, shelter and proper security no matter the status of life of the husband. On the other hand, the role of the household amounts to an act of charity and therefore, the woman will be rewarded by God. Divine texts from the verves of the Quran and the Sunnah explain the right to fair treatment under polygamy marriage arrangement.⁷² Other rights which Muslim women enjoy under marital jurisprudence include the right to ownership of property, whether moveable or immoveable assets and the right to dispose such property without necessarily involving a third party. Above all Muslim women under Islamic law enjoy economic rights

⁶⁴ Yusuf, H.Bilkisu. (Ed.) *Sexuality and the Marriage Institution in Islam: An Appraisal*. Understanding Human Sexuality Seminar Series 4, Africa Regional Sexuality Resource Center, Lagos, June 9, 2005, pp. 1-19.

⁶⁵ Q 30: 21 and Q 16:72.

⁶⁶ Q 7:189.

⁶⁷ Abu Al-Baqā Ayub, Al-Kulliyat. 2nd edn, Cairo, Dar Al-Kitab Al-Islami, 1992, p. 486.

⁶⁸ El-Alami, Dawoud. *The Marriage Contract in Islamic Law*. Kluwer Academic Publishers, 1992, p.10.

⁶⁹ Abdal 'Ati, Hummudah *The Family Structure in Islam*. Lagos, Islamic Publications Bureau, 1982, p.54. El-Alami, Dawoud. *The Marriage Contract in Islamic Law*. Kluwer Academic Publishers, 1992, p.10.

⁷⁰ Said, Mansur Ibrahim. *The Influence of Culture and Tradition in Divorce: Implications for Marital Stability in the Rights of Widows and Divorce in Hausa-Fulani Society*. Mahnufashi, Ibrahim A and Yakasai, Salisu A. (Eds.), Sokoto, Garkuwa Media Services, 2002.

⁷¹ Yusuf, H.Bilkisu, .Op.cit, p.13.

⁷² Ibid, p.15-17.

during marriage.⁷³ One of vital ingredient of Muslim marriage is the provision of marriage gift, usually from the man to the woman which may be in cash or any asset, such gift is mainly to the wife.⁷⁴ The woman sole responsibility in Muslim marriage is taking care of the children and the home. Despite such responsibilities women are allowed to work outside the domestic frontier provided the home do not suffer any set back.⁷⁵

Furthermore, Muslim women have the right to partake in politics and governance. Thereby has the right to vote and be voted for in any capacity whatsoever. In addition, she has the rights to express her at home and even in party politics.⁷⁶ Similarly, Muslim women also enjoy the rights to be involved in Islamic political decision-making bodies referred to as *shura*. To this end women are involved in decision making process be it at domestic or political levels of human engagement.⁷⁷ Fundamentally, women are expected to show absolute respect to the head of the household, the husband and assist in the proper home training of the children. To see to the cleanliness of the home and make the home peaceful at all times.⁷⁸ Orthodox scholars are of the opinion that one of the beauties of Islamic marriage is that it ensures intimacy, affinity and tranquility. In a nutshell, intimacy love and comfort are vital value of marriage.⁷⁹

On the other hand, other intellectuals argue that Muslim marriage assist the husband and wife to be psychologically settled and enjoy peace on the long run. Muslim marriage encourages the spread of love and intimacy to the relatives of not only the wife but to the neighbors of the couple thereby promoting peaceful co-existence with security and peace.⁸⁰ In addition, it assists in the preservation of mankind via procreation and continuity of human race. This is the offspring of the union form part of the pivot of supporting the husband and wife when their children come of age in the near future. If not according to Muslim intellectuals the structure of human race will be unbalance if not extinct.⁸¹ Islamic marriage ensures legal framework of protecting the moral values of both the man and woman. This ultimately protects human dignity and assists in the well-being of the human race.⁸²

One school of thought, argues that there are three main aims that marriage seeks to achieve, namely: protecting the human race, safeguarding the release of psychological

⁷³ Ibid, p.18.

⁷⁴ Q 4:24.

⁷⁵ Op.cit, p.19.

⁷⁶ Ibid, p.20.

⁷⁷ Al-Ghazali, Muhammad. *Ihya 'ulum al-din*. Vol. 2, 2nd Ed. Ibrahim, Sayyid. (ed.), Cairo, Dar Al-Hadith, 1990, p. 49.

⁷⁸ Q 3:104.

⁷⁹ Al-Ghazali, Muhammad. *Ihya 'ulum al-din*. Vol. 2, 2nd Ed. Ibrahim, Sayyid. (ed.), Cairo, Dar Al-Hadith, 1990, p. 49.

⁸⁰ Bin Humayd, Sahih, et al. *mawsu'at nidrat al-Naim*. Vol. 2, Jeddah, Dar Al-Wasilah, 1988, p. 497. Al-Mawdudi, Abu Ala-Ala. *Huquq al-Zawjain*, trans Idris, Ahmad. Cairo, Maktabat Al-Quran, n.d, p.19.

⁸¹ Ibid, p. 500.

⁸² Ibid, p. 501.

tension and promoting enjoyment for the hope of fulfilling the sole aim of Muslims, which is to reside in paradise on the last day.⁸³ Another value of the Muslim marriage is that it enables adherents to establish families based on Islamic legal framework.⁸⁴ The family is seen as the pillar of human society and marriage is regarded as a means whereby the husband and wife are tutored on how to be responsible couples. Thus, couples try to work hard so that they can fend for their family.⁸⁵ In the long run, besides providing a meaningful life for the man, the marriage is expected to provide for the well-being, security and other needs of the wife.⁸⁶

9. OVERVIEW OF A RECENTLY DECIDED CASE ON ISLAMIC MARRIAGE

This section of the paper reviews a case on Islamic marriage decided by the Islamic courts in Zanzibar. Although unreported, the case deals with the rights and duties of parties to a marriage under Islamic law.

9.1 Rights and duties of parties to a marriage: Halima Bilali Issa V. Khatib Ali Issa.⁸⁷

The complaint of the claimant was about marriage and maintenance. The parties were married under Islamic law and lived together. After a while, the relationship between husband and wife became strained. The husband became highhanded, abusive and resorted to the use of vulgar language on his wife. His wife responded with equal toxicity. Out of anger and frustration, the woman requested for divorce, which her husband immediately pronounced. Following the pronouncement of talaq, she moved out of their matrimonial home for her parent's home. However, in less than seven days after her departure, her husband sought for reconciliation and settlement of their dispute. This overture was resisted with hostility from the woman's parents. Furthermore, they accused the man of failing to pay the outstanding dowry, which the husband pledged to pay as soon as possible. The Islamic court highlighted the shortcomings of both the husband and wife.

The court noted that although the husband appeared intelligent and mature, he lacked enough patience and tolerance to cope with his wife's emotional outbursts over marital matters. These shortcomings, the court remarked, were the mistakes of the husband. The court observed that his wife made similar mistakes, and blamed her too. The court pointed out that it was a red flag for the husband to make the pronouncement of talaq even under provocation. This according to the court did not portray the husband as a good Muslim. The court said that the husband should have intimated his wife of his desire for reconciliation before reporting at her family house on the matter. However, the court that the reversal of the talaq was consistent with *Shafii* jurisprudence.

⁸³ Al-Sharbini, Muhammad. *Mughni al-Muhtaj ila ma'rifat ma ani alfaz al-Muhtaj*. Vol. 3, Cairo, Matba Mustafa Al-Babi, 1985, p. 124. See also abdal Ati, Hummudah. *The Family Structure in Islam*. Indiana, American Trust Publications, 1977, p. 50.

⁸⁴ Al-Mawdudi, Abu Al-Ala. *Nizam al-Hayat fi al-Islam*. Riyadh, Al-Dar Al-Saudiah li al-nashr wa al-tawzi. 1987, p.51-52.

⁸⁵ Ibid.

⁸⁶ Uthman, Ahmad. *Athar aqd al-zawaj fi al-shariah al-Islamiyyah*. Riyadh, 1981, p. 19.

⁸⁷ This is an Unreported, Kadhis Court Mfenesi Case Number 18/2012.

On the other hand, the court advised the wife to always watch her words or language. Provocative and use of vulgar words only escalate marital disputes. And importantly, the wife must always control her emotions, particularly on matters related to their marriage. The court cautioned in-laws to the husband about their conduct, and its tendency to escalate the dispute. The Islamic court highlighted terms and conditions of marital union under the *Shafii* jurisprudence to the couple. Also, it explained the waiting period or the *iddah* period after *talaq* under *Shafii* jurisprudence. The court pointed out that instant reversal of *talaq* is a recognized norm under *Shafii* jurisprudence. Furthermore, *Shafii* jurisprudence provides for reconciliation whenever there is a dispute between husband and wife. This is to ensure peaceful co-existence in the marriage.

10. CONCLUSION

The paper examined the impact of *shafii* jurisprudence on marriage guardianship on Islamic courts in Zanzibar. The discourse focused on marriage guardianship in Islam; the divine position and guardianship as a necessary ingredient of Muslim marriage. Similarly, the paper conducted an overview of marriage guardianship under Islamic law and the position of *shafii* jurisprudence. In addition, juristic arguments were presented on the issue, and the significance of Muslim marriage identified. Lastly, a review of one judicial decision from the Islamic court in Zanzibar was carried out.